

Exploring the Predictive Efficacy of the K-Nearest Neighbors Algorithm Using Genetic and Pharmacological Data From Cancer Cell Lines

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Abstract

Although heterogeneity in cancer cell response to drugs continues to represent a significant barrier to anti-cancer agent development and testing, machine learning, particularly KNN models, has shown promise in prediction using pharmacological and genetic profiles. However, optimization of KNN parameters, notably neighborhood size or k , and unforeseen structural trends and limitations remain as key questions in application to cancer cell lines. This study aims to examine patterns, optimizations, and relationships to biological intuition and relevance in the context of drug sensitivity and cancer cell heterogeneity in this limited investigation of KNN considering only the drug Camptothecin as a reference with a blindly chosen cell line, EW-11. It was found that smaller k values leading to disproportionately inaccurate results could likely be attributed to molecularly similar yet pharmacologically different cell lines. A degree of robustness in ranking, insensitive to even doubling intuitive parameters such as mutations, was observed, and an increased Euclidean distance to distinguish similar lines had a positive effect. A k of 14 was found to be optimized for cell line EW-11. Yet, this was not generalizable to other randomly chosen cell lines, likely due to different biological cluster sizes. However, a k of 14 yielded a relatively accurate prediction for the nearest neighbor of EW-11, supporting the notion that an optimized k value accounts for the size of a local subgroup. Further investigations are necessary to expand these implications and continue to refine the capacities of a KNN model.

1. Introduction

Heterogeneous responses to pharmacological agents remain a fundamental quality among various types of cancer cells and pose a considerable challenge to treatment synthesis and development. This heterogeneity, even among seemingly similar tumor types and individual cells, has long represented the need for slow, direct drug testing on a one-to-one basis to establish a reliable drug efficacy profile.¹ Despite this, certain aspects of cancer cell lines, such as similarities and differences among fine genetic profiles and mutation characteristics such as copy number alteration, continue to hold significance in drug sensitivity analysis and indicate that such heterogeneity, though not simple to track, is not randomly distributed.² Indeed, the importance of analyzing these features has been shown in numerous studies, and the validity of analyzing other cancer cell lines and highlighting genetic aberrations in an attempt to group cancer cells remains a promising field of study in the world of pharmacological prediction.³

Machine learning has shown increasing promise in various applications, and the field of cancer cell pharmacology is no exception. In fact, numerous studies have investigated the efficacy and potential of a machine learning algorithm to predict drug response, especially given genetic profiles.⁴ In particular, k-nearest-neighbors (KNN), a model known for its relatively simple and interpretable method among machine learning algorithms, has received recent attention in its ability to perform predictions on cancer-drug relationships when given a smaller set of genes in the 10s and 100s.⁵ Though application of KNN has shown promise when applied to pharmacological data, optimization of KNN parameters, especially neighborhood size (k) or the number of nearest neighbors to be considered in prediction, remains critical to algorithmic performance as KNN sensitivity depends on these settings.⁶ Ultimately, though KNN has shown potential in the field of machine learning applications in various contexts within medicine, optimization of KNN parameters and efficacy when handling up to tens of thousands of genes remains a key question and barrier to widespread generalization, especially into an area of study as heterogeneous as cancer cell behavior, with respect to drug sensitivity.

Here, we aim to investigate the applicability and efficacy of a KNN model in the field of cancer-drug predictions by examining neighborhood size, feature scaling, and mutation weighting in exploratory analysis. An emphasis on the generalizability of optimal settings and the connection to cancer cell heterogeneity would also be made in this study's experimentation. Though the study offers a limited scope into the vast world of KNN, it is hoped that trends and observations in KNN parameters and k optimization with respect to biological intuition and relevance reveal key dynamics, strengths, and limitations in this machine learning model.

2. Methods

2.1. Data Acquisition

Data on the genetic and pharmacological profiles of various cancer cell lines were exported from the Genomics of Drug Sensitivity in Cancer (GDSC2 version), developed through a collaboration between the Wellcome Sanger Institute (UK) and the Massachusetts General Hospital Cancer Center (USA).⁷ Data from the category “Genetic Features” and “Drug Data” for pan-cancer tissues were selected to add both genetic and pharmacological dimensionality in terms of LN_IC50 (the log of an IC50 value correlating to pharmacological efficacy).

2.2. Data Processing

Python 3 libraries using Jupyter were used in the data processing phase to make the information compatible with KNN using Euclidean distance. The raw drug data was truncated to only include the following parameters: COSMIC_ID (which was determined as a suitable cancer cell line identifier to be shared across both genetic and pharmacological profiles), DRUG_ID, and LN_IC50. The data frame was adjusted to ensure that each row represented a specific instance of a cancer cell line tested with a certain drug. The genetic data was truncated to contain the following parameters based on biological relevance determined by this study: COSMIC_ID, IS_Mutated (the status of whether the genes were mutated in that cell line), Recurrent Gain Loss (change in copy number variation), and Genes in Segment (the genes deemed relevant). The data was processed so each row would contain a specific instance of a cancer cell line, a specific gene, a recurrent status, and whether it was classified as a mutated state by the original publication. Data was filtered to remove any null values before KNN modeling that would be incompatible, and the status of the three genetic parameters mentioned was made numerical, which were all standardized to a scale of 1 and 0. The pharmacological data and the genetic data were then merged into one data table on COSMIC_ID, creating input rows connecting drug performance to a genetic profile that would be fed into the KNN algorithm.

2.3. KNN Development

This study utilized the sklearn.neighbors Python library and imported the Python-compatible KNeighborsRegressor. Euclidean distance was used as a default. With variables stored for the drug of interest and the cancer cell line of interest, the code preceding the KNN model only chose KNN training data that contained instances of that specific drug on other cancer cell lines to ensure the model only took data of that drug into consideration. The data value of the drug of interest on the cancer cell line of interest was excluded to prevent data leakage and was used as the provided data for comparison. The profile of the cancer cell line of interest was extracted separately in another function to act as the input for the KNN model post drug-specific training to generate a predictive value. Due to the vast nature of the data and the numerous drugs that would be infeasible to investigate in this study, Camptothecin was blindly chosen by DRUG_ID without selection bias to be the drug of reference for which this model would be tested, and EW-11 was also chosen blindly by COSMIC_ID to begin the investigation.

3. Results

3.1. Exploratory Sensitivity Testing of KNN Parameters

An exploration phase was conducted on the KNN model generated handling EW-11 and Camptothecin during the fine-tuning phase of model development. Throughout this process, key KNN parameters and aspects of the processed data were intentionally perturbed to observe the change in sensitivity and predictive behavior of the KNN model with theoretical optimization. Using the value from the original data source as a reference, an absolute error between the provided and predicted LN_{IC50} values and the percent error were calculated for each condition as noted below. A starting point of $k=5$ as the number of nearest neighbors in a Euclidean distance model that would be considered in the predictive model was chosen to begin exploration. At $k=5$, the model exhibited poor performance overall before any further changes were made, which in a relatively small neighborhood cluster that theoretically would find similar cancer cell lines by drug performance and genetic profile, possibly indicates the presence of a molecularly similar but pharmacologically different cell line with respect to Camptothecin. Scaling the difference between the positive and negative conditions of the three genetic parameters to increase the numerical difference between the two states was done to increase the algorithmic distance between similar features and distinct cell lines, and this had a marginally positive effect in this instance. This optimization was deemed necessary to be applied throughout the study based on the hypothesis that a raw score distance of two would filter out distinct cell lines more effectively compared to a distance of one between absence and presence. Based on the biological relevance of the presence of a mutated gene from wild type in many cancer cell lines, an exploratory modification of multiplying the mutation weighting by a factor of two was done to test whether this would create a meaningful difference if the nearest neighbors were kept at $k=5$. No difference at all, even to the maximum significant figure returned by the algorithm, was observed, indicating a degree of inherent robustness to the similarity rankings the KNN model was producing, even without this modification. Finally, to investigate the validity of a molecularly similar outlier that may have resulted in an unfavorable outcome for the KNN model, rather than the model itself being flawed, a smaller $k=3$ was tested. Holding all other parameters constant, a smaller neighborhood cluster of $k=3$ yielded far worse results, further reinforcing the possibility that there is a molecularly similar outlier very close to the cell line of interest that is skewing predictions. Considering these outcomes, an exploration into the optimal neighborhood cluster size and the examination of this possible outlier were done to investigate whether the poor results stemmed from this hypothesis or were an inherent fault of the algorithm at a fundamental level. Neither notion could be ruled out nor supported at this stage.

Table 1. Predictive Outcome of Exploratory KNN Algorithmic Parameter Modifications on Cell Line EW-11 with Camptothecin.

Conditions	LN_IC50	Absolute Error	Percent Error ^a
Provided Data	-3.742	N/A	N/A
k ^b =5	-2.827	0.915	149.727%
k=5 0 → ^c -1	-2.832	0.910	148.491%
k=5 0 → -1 MUT x2	-2.832	0.910	148.491%
k=3 0 → -1 MUT ^d x2 ^e	-2.263	1.478	338.665%

^aAs LN_IC50 is represented in the log space, thus distorting the percentage values, the percent error was calculated from the difference in IC50 between the predicted and experimental values.

^bk represents the number of nearest neighbors being considered for the KNN algorithm.

^cRepresents the change in the (-) or absence value from 0 to -1 to increase the difference and aid differentiation in Euclidean calculations.

^dMUT represents the mutations parameter, representing every gene in the status of “mutated” (represented by “1” before modification) or “unmutated” (represented by “0” before modification).

^eRepresents multiplying the mutation numerical vector by a factor of two to increase the weight of mutated genes.

3.2. Optimization of Nearest Neighbor Cluster Sizes of EW-11 and Camptothecin

The KNN model was run with varying k values to explore the location and presence of a possible outlier extremely close to the cell line in algorithmic ranking and the optimal k nearest neighbor cluster for this particular cell line and drug combination. Various nearest neighbor cluster values were tested with the model. Firstly, running a KNN model on the nearest neighbor only ($k=1$), expectedly, yielded a reasonable prediction relative to published figures. However, expanding the neighborhood to simply $k=2$ yielded significantly worse results, and the percent error increased by more than a factor of 10, further reinforcing the validity that a molecularly similar but pharmacologically different outlier is present and implying that the second nearest neighbor position was a very likely outlier, as its addition alone drastically increased the error. Chronologically, a KNN model was run using k values of 10, 15, 20, and 25, and among these experimentations to determine the optimal nearest neighbor cluster, the error given by using a k value of 15 was the lowest. Accordingly, further trial runs were expanded from this focal point, resulting in trial runs with k values 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, and 18. Among these, a k value of 14 yielded the most optimal results outside of the single nearest neighbor, with errors getting worse as the k value decreased or increased. Given the trends, the KNN model expresses strong evidence that a k value of 14 is the optimized nearest neighbor cluster to generate the most accurate prediction in this specific instance. However, the generalizability of this “14-Hypothesis” to other blindly chosen cell lines was tested further.

Table 2. Predictive Outcome of Varying KNN Cluster Sizes on Cell Line EW-11 with Camptothecin.

Conditions	LN_IC50	Absolute Error	Percent Error
Provided Data	-3.742	N/A	N/A
k=1	-3.440	0.301	35.188%
k=2	-2.155	1.587	388.759%
k=10	-3.282	0.460	58.478%
k=12	-3.149	0.593	81.005%
k=13	-3.297	0.445	56.044%
k=14	-3.370	0.372	45.073%
k=15	-3.342	0.400	49.196%
k=16	-3.215	0.527	69.449%
k=17	-3.116	0.626	87.070%
k=18	-3.121	0.621	85.991%
k=20	-3.082	0.660	93.406%
k=25	-2.902	0.840	131.595%

3.3. Extrapolation of the “14-Hypothesis” on PFSK-1 and ES7

To explore the validity of the “14-Hypothesis” and examine whether this finding was generalizable to other blindly chosen cell lines, PFSK-1 and ES7 were selected. The KNN model was applied with a k=14 nearest neighbor cluster, consistent with the previous findings, to test whether a relatively low percent error could be achieved and if the prediction algorithm could perform well in other cell lines and, inevitably, other cell clusters. The KNN model performed poorly with both cell lines. Notably, the application of the “14-Hypothesis” on cell line ES7 proved particularly inaccurate, with a percent error of over 1000%. Considering the results of this failed application of this hypothesis on two randomly selected cell lines, the generalizability of this finding was implied to be limited to the specific EW-11 and Camptothecin relationship. Despite these results, it was deemed necessary to observe whether this trend that k=14 gave the best results was specific to only the specific EW-11 cell line, or if it could perhaps be used in its local cluster, such as its most biologically similar neighbor according to the KNN algorithm.

Table 3. Predictive Outcome of the KNN Model with a Cluster Size of 14 on PFSK-1 with Camptothecin.

Conditions	LN_IC50	Absolute Error	Percent Error
Provided Data	-1.464	N/A	N/A
k=14	-2.519	1.055	187.245%

Table 4. Predictive Outcome of the KNN Model with a Cluster Size of 14 on ES7 with Camptothecin.

Conditions	LN_IC50	Absolute Error	Percent Error
Provided Data	-5.045	N/A	N/A
k=14	-2.428	2.618	1269.755%

3.4. Observing the “14-Hypothesis” on the Nearest Neighbor of EW-11

The nearest neighbor to EW-11 was found by modifying the KNN algorithm to process the predictive value with a $k=1$ value and then outputting the nearest neighbor used in the calculation. The output of LB2241-RCC was further confirmed to be accurate by cross-validating the established LB2241-RCC LN_IC50 value with Camptothecin with the predicted value when $k=1$. Both values lined up exactly. Promisingly, the KNN model generated a relatively accurate prediction when using $k=14$, even more accurate than the cell line that gave rise to this implied “14-Hypothesis.” The very high efficacy of the KNN model when applying this “14-Hypothesis” on a cell line that can be considered as part of the original cell line’s (EW-11) “cluster” indicates that optimal nearest neighbor sizes used in KNN models may be generalizable not just to that specific cell line but to the local subcluster of similar cell lines itself as it can capture the rough biological cluster size of that group in the KNN model. This line of reasoning remains consistent with the inability of the “14-Hypothesis” to be generalizable on random cell lines, as those clusters likely have different biological sizes outright. Therefore, the nearest neighbor size is not optimized to handle that specific group of similar cancer cells.

Table 5. Predictive Outcome of the KNN Model with a Cluster Size of 14 on LB2241-RCC with Camptothecin.

Conditions	LN_IC50	Absolute Error	Percent Error
Provided Data	-3.440	N/A	N/A
$k=14$	-3.232	0.209	23.228%

4. Discussion

In this limited exploration of genetic and pharmacological cancer cell data using a KNN algorithm, multiple trends were noted in the exploratory phase. The scaling of differences between a positive and negative indication on the three genetic profiles to increase the difference between a similar and nonsimilar cancer cell line had a marginal benefit consistent with expected intuition. Doubling the weighting of mutations, which are typically biologically significant and can be a relevant differentiating factor, did not impact the results, likely indicating that the KNN categorization had a degree of robustness in the genetic profile. Smaller-sized clusters led to significant deviations from the predicted value for EW-11, which indicates either a low efficacy for the KNN model as a whole, as a smaller neighborhood of similar cells would be expected to yield more accurate results, or the possibility of a molecularly similar but pharmacologically different outlier with respect to Camptothecin. Due to the vast number of genes accounted for, it is possible from a cellular biology standpoint that this outlier could have similarities with EW-11 in many genes, but is not similar in the few pathway-specific genes that matter for Camptothecin, resulting in a “similar” cell line that is also not similar in Camptothecin IC₅₀. This observation represents a critical limitation of a simple KNN model. Not all genes and pharmacological relationships are going to be completely equally relevant to predictions for a specific type of drug that inevitably only impacts a fraction of those genes. The presence of this outlier is later validated with future predictive outcomes targeting intentionally smaller neighborhood clusters, underscoring a key limitation of the KNN model in cancer cell application and the necessity for models to account for and possibly remove outliers when biologically defensible to come to a more accurate result.

This study also attempted to find the optimized nearest neighbor cluster size for KNN predictions for EW-11 with Camptothecin. The most accurate prediction and the lowest percent error was achieved with $k=14$, with increasing errors as this cluster size increased or decreased in both directions. This could imply, from a biological standpoint, that there is a local cluster of about 14 or so cancer cells that share similar traits, as expansion beyond this number decreases the accuracy and predictive power, indicating an increased level of noise or more cell lines that are not as similar. The notion that cancer cells could have groups that are similar in molecular profile is consistent with these findings and likely can be represented in a simple KNN model.

The applicability, however, of this “14-Hypothesis” proved to be inconsistent and inadequate, especially for cancer cells chosen at random. The KNN model failed to capture an accurate prediction when tested with blindly chosen cancer cells with respect to Camptothecin and yielded errors that were, in some instances, over 1000%. This study proposes the link between the failure of the “14-Hypothesis” to be generalizable and the principle that cancer cell subgroups have likely inherently different sizes. Therefore, the threshold to adequately capture the size of a subgroup in terms of the number of nearest neighbors is likely not a generalizable variable among various types of cancer cell lines, at least within the limitations of a simple KNN model.

Despite these shortcomings in testing other cancer cell lines, the model did show a relatively strong performance when the “14-Hypothesis” finding was extrapolated to the nearest

neighbor of that cell line. This further reinforces the notion that there appear to be localized clusters of cancer cells that have a somewhat fixed group size, and that this group of cancer cells may share an optimal number of nearest neighbors, which the KNN model should consider. Ultimately, the data suggests that the KNN model can possibly be generalized to a cluster rather than an individual cancer cell line, and that the parameter that is unique between each optimized KNN model for a particular group is the size of said group.

Further study and exploration are needed to confirm and generalize some of the trends and biological relationships mentioned in this study. The data presented represents a limited view into the vast relationships between genetic and pharmacological data through the lens of Camptothecin, and further machine learning investigations must be done to test the findings proposed. However, the study aimed to examine and identify interesting correlations and trends to expand avenues for future study into KNN models, and hoped to capture key limitations in terms of biological relevance. Though the application of a widespread KNN model to various types of cancer cells may seem difficult based on the results of this particular study, the potential for a more complex and fine KNN model to account for the limitations suggested here cannot be understated, especially in a world where the application of machine learning and prediction algorithms in the field of medicine will continue to grow.

5. Conclusion

Here, this study examined the application and predictive ability of a simple KNN model on genetic and pharmacological data with the aim of observing trends, patterns, and limitations in the context of biological relevance and cancer-drug behavior. The robustness of the KNN model in the categorical ranking of cancer cell lines was observed due to the lack of any effective change by doubling mutation weighting, and an increase in Euclidean distance did yield marginally positive results. The presence of molecularly similar outliers was observed in smaller k values, representing a key limitation of a simple KNN model due to its inability to discern which genes may be impacted the most by the drug of interest. Although an optimized k value was found, it was only generalizable and produced acceptable results for the nearest neighbor of that cell line, indicating that an optimal k value may correlate with the size of a local biological cluster. Future studies on the relationship between the KNN model and these proposed principles and trends are necessary due to the inherently limited scope of this study.

6. References

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